

Pathways to openness in Networked Learning research: The case of Open Data

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Juliana E. Raffaghelli

It was an enchanting morning of May and we were a tiny group of 9, but we were all prepared to work.

We opened the session as expected with a roundtable. Some of the participants were just colleagues supporting me (2); from the remaining 7, all from North Europe (UK, Denmark, Netherlands) they were between the genuine curiosity about what they declared to be a new topic and the position of wanting something less theoretical than the classical congress presentations.

The participants also covered a wide range of professional expertise, and were mostly experienced researchers.

Between the topics of interest and actual work, the participants mentioned: Open Educational practices, Higher Education and Learning Design, Educational technology, universal design, collaborative learning, language and translation, evaluation and assessment.

With good representation between males, females and other

Gender

9 responses

I took about 20 minutes to make my presentation, and hence, we started with the work I had prepared.

Firstly, we dig into the participants' knowledge about Open Data. My position there was that we should acknowledge a baseline in order to undertake a more reflective and critical work.

We started with a brief analysis of open data practices, which results I immediately shared. The idea was to comment on some of such results.

The first question was about how much the participants knew about Open Data. In a scale ranging from 1 to 10, most placed between 4-7, which was like there were lots of questions about the topic, but some general idea around.

How much do I know about Open Data

9 responses

We discussed later around this expertise. All the participants were aware of Open Access as part of Open Science policies. However, the practical approach to open data (preparing, publishing, sharing data and working over second-hand data) was not so clear. The people with responses 4-6 did not know about platforms to publish open data. In part, as the debate went over, they said the institutions were not promoting a relating debate.

When coming to explore the methods from which data was get in the respective research activities, a picture of complexity and diversity emerged. Most methods related to textual and

discursive sources which, differently from other disciplinary fields (as one of the participants said) were not easy to open and share in case that was the intention.

From the other side, another issue discussed was that in our field of research, most data collected cannot be commodified (as in the fields of biomedicine or engineering). Therefore, they would feel more degrees of freedom as researchers in doing so.

From which methods do I obtain my data?

Methods to collect data: Interviews, Online Forum, Text Mining, Social Networks (crawling or manually extracting), Ethnographic observation/participation, narrative approaches, learning analytics, educational interventions...among others. It was clear that the preferred form were the interviews, but when asked about text mining and web crawling, all the participants exchanged visions about the blurring borders of ethics in collecting data from public websites: If a person or student leave their data on a social network, even if it's public, can it be collected and processed for research? This was not the original purpose. However, another researcher (expert in social networks) told that one bigger problem was the data which could not be accessed due to the obscure forms of data processing by social networks. It appears that data which can be necessary for research purposes (and hence for good, hopefully!) is more and more difficult to get (due to ethical concerns and procedures) whereas for the companies such data is easily available. Whose data, which openness, which access? This was a problem which we left...open for further debate!

So we moved to the social activity around data: did the participants share their data? When and how?

My Data Sharing Approach: How?

9 responses

Labels in the figure:

- I do not share my data with anyone
- I share with my immediate collaborators
- I share with others in my institution
- I share with scientists/educational technologists in my field
- I share with scientists/professionals in other fields
- I share with participants
- I share with my students, to teach and learn on a topic
- I share with interested people in the society

It was possible to observe that sharing data was a rather restricted activity, connected to tight professional groups (66,7% share with immediate collaborators, against 22,2% sharing with participants or students). When we discussed this results, the participants mentioned their conflict between a system (the academia) that requests productivity and is highly competitive; and the ideal situation in which data can be shared with students and participants as democratic approach. They all saw this scenario as ideal but unrealisable at the current state of affairs.

We moved hence to the next question, connected to the best situation/moment to share data.

My Data Sharing approach: When?

9 responses

Labels in the figure:

- Never, I don't consider it appropriate
- Never, until now, but I would do it in the future
- Immediately after the data have been generated
- After the data have been normalized and/or corrected for errors
- After the data have been analysed
- With my publication (report or paper)
- After (a period of time) the findings derived from this data have been published

For the same reasons commented above, the researchers considered appropriate to share their data with the publication. Since the final publication is the product to which the system gives value, opening data is just luxury. If there is no recognition of open data practices, the participants agreed in the difficult (though ideal) situation they have to face to share data. In any case, one participant mentioned the “pushing” phenomenon of journals asking for open datasets (it was mentioned a special issue about open data by the British Journal of Educational Technologies). The rest of the participants were between the sceptical and the curious about such resource.

The question relating the agenda of Open Data in the field (*effective actions to take in the short term to advance the agenda of an Open Data in our field [NWL/EdTech community] are...*) raised full consensus: the more the policies and institutional context advances, the more the researchers and practitioners will be willing of improving their data literacy levels.

Interdisciplinary work might help: some of the researchers collaborating with other fields like STEM education, mentioned the more open approach in Physics.

10. In my view, effective actions to take in the short term to advance the agenda of an Open Data in our field [NWL/EdTech community] are... *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Completely ineffective	Rather ineffective	Neutral	Rather effective	Completely effective
Improve researchers and practitioners' "data literacy" through faculty development and other institutional policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improve the availability of tools for self-diagnosis and self-learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strengthen International, European and National policies for Open Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Strengthen researchers' awareness through the NWL specific community, with activities, discussion groups, communities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Promote dialogue between other disciplines, understanding their OD agenda, to improve the visibility of Educational Research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Note: the figure represents the “median” of opinions between the nine participants, corrected upon the discussion and agreed in this second instance of “member checking”, beyond the individual responses.

It was hence the turn of the “Open Data Expedition”: we went to discover ZENODO, FIGSHARE, OPENAIRE, MENDELEY, among other open data platforms. This activity lasted just 20 minutes of individual user experience, so we could not expect deep insights, but an initial approach to the platforms. Most researchers did not know the specific open data repositories (like ZENODO) whereas they were well aware about Research Gate or Academia.

Some of the comments were that educational data was not easy to retrieve; that metadata was not detailed enough; that they retrieved rather papers than data...and the like. When we discussed about these issues, the participants agreed on the relevance of producing and correctly publishing Open Data, for further use. At the current state of things, the low quality and the little availability of Open Data from the educational field might prevent them to take any advantage for their research activities.

The last activity we arrived to introduce was the collective “mapping” of the current state of things. The idea of this activity, based on a quadrant graph, was to “place” themselves in a continuum between two pair of tensions: the personal willingness and motivation to engage in the open data/open science movement, and the institutional support and availability of resources to do so.

The image shows the several subjective positionings, as opinion by the participants around the way they saw not only themselves but other researchers in their respective institutions and field of research. The vertical axis represents the institutional support, and the horizontal axis, the personal motivation to engage in open data practices.

It appears clearly that at the current state of affairs, the advancement depends mostly over the personal motivation, more than the perceived institutional support. When I asked about these positionings in the map, the researchers told me that they saw mostly idealistic discourses coming mostly from the transnational policy making (particularly, EU research projects). Again, without a clear institutional and national policy rewarding the academics for publishing, sharing and making their data usable by the society, this is just a personal endeavour.

I final reflection I made while writing these notes was that what the researchers were referring to a personal commitment...and this mostly take the form of activism. Activism is the driving force of change, a bottom up movement to transform what is seen as unfair, or outdated, or not responding to the needs or values of participants. It appeared to me that some of the participants were willing to embrace a more open and participatory ways of doing research, but the context did not help them in such endeavour. From the other side, some of the participants saw this effort as pure utopia.

In any case, what could I do next? Which could be my next move? I would certainly ask to younger researchers about their willing to transform their practice in the direction of what has been called the “post-academic science”(Ziman, 1996). From the other side, I would be curious about how the educators could engage with open research data: is thi

References

Ziman, J. (1996). “Post-Academic Science”: Constructing Knowledge with Networks and Norms. *Science & Technology Studies*, 9(1), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.55095>